

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Survey and revision of leaf miners to some plants from different localities of Iraq

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Abstract

This investigation showed (31) species belonging to (15) genera under (five) families and two orders. The leafminers Dipter families (Agromozidae, Anthomyiidae, Drosophilidae), Agromyzid flies is the highest level of investigated many host plants, but other families have lowest host plants. The synonyms of species were provided from GBIF scarlet's. The date and localities of sampling collection were recorded.

Keywords: Leaf miners; Agromyzidae; Anthomyiidae; Drosophilidae; Lepidoptera; Iraq

1. Introduction

The leaf miner, showed any of insect larvae which habitats and feed in leaf plants. The miners include caterpillars of some lepidopterans (Order Lepidoptera), sawfly larvae (Order Hymenoptera), beetle and weevil grubs or larvae (order Coleoptera), and maggots (larvae) of true flies (order Diptera) [1]

Most leaf-miner of order Diptera is Family Agromyzidae made burrows or tunnels in leaves of host plants, some of them are stem borer with galls maker [2]. This family is widely distributed at the world with loss species southern part of hemisphere than in hot areas of Nearctic and Palearctic regions then it had many studies in deferent localities of the world [3, 4].

Agromyzidae consist of more than 2,500 species round the world, its member's small with wing length 2-3mm in maximum about 6.5mm. The adults can be diagnosed with characters; head sclerotizes and the upper part of frons lightly sclerotized and loss seta, but the lower and dorsal of head with more heavily sclerotized with setulae and pubescent, frontal vita sometimes made patch and tuff in different colors compare with the rest of head. The frons with 1-7 frontal bristles, with presence of vibrissae. Compound eyes ovate in shape, small usually but in some species circular and large. Wings usually hyaline, often with marks (dark spots and shaped) of tropical species. Costal vein has break on the apex of subcost; cup cell small; 1st anal vein not reached the wing margin. Abdomen has patch and color spot on tergites in male using to differ from species, female abdomen fused tergal (T 6-8) which has two spiracles located between (T5 and genital segment) while the seventh one forming an oviscape. [2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9].

Family Anthomyiidae is one of the most important flies which distributes at all the zoogeographical region. They found with deferent conditions from vegetables, dead animals and most of them phytophagous caused injuries and damaged plants, such genera *Delia* and *Pegomya*; (*Pegomya hyoscami* species group). Some species had economic importance which infested cultivated crops [10].

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The Spinach leafminer *Pegomya hyoscyami* small fly, female inserted ovipositor and laid eggs on leaf surface and maggot made tunnel on it. Larvae whit maggot caused blotches, then pupal stage and adults emerge in spring from soil. [11].

The family Drosophilidae is a cosmopolitan of acalyprate consists of more than 3,950 species [12]. The important genus is *Scaptomyza* Hardy, a lot of species belong to it as leaf miners. *Scaptomyza flava* is an alienate species of European origin [13]

The most important lepidopteran leafminers (Tomota Leaf miner and Citrus leaf miner). Which economically importance. *Tuta absoluta* is phytophagus insect attacking Solanaceae family plants [14].

2. Material and methods

Many infested leaf of plants were collected from different Localities of Iraq, (25-40) leaves per each plants) during 2020 year. The collecting leaves were brought to the department of Entomology and Invertebrates at Iraq Natural History Research Center and Museum, then kept in Petri Dishes under room temperature. The dishes were labeled and the places and date of collecting were recorded. After 2-3 weeks the insect left leaves as adults.

The plants and insects of orders Diptera and Lepidoptera were diagnosed by authors and used taxonomical keys such as: [2, 8, 10, 11] The specimens were storage at department of Entomology and invertebrate.

3. Results and discussion

This investigation showed (31) species belonging to (15) genera under (5) families with two orders (Diptera and Lepidoptera) as follow:

Order, Diptera

Family, Agromyzidae

Subfamily, Agromyzinae

Genus, *Agromyza* Fallén, 1810

Synonyms: *Adromyza* Meigen, 1830

Calyptomyza Hardy, 1850

Mesonevra Lioy, 1864

Stomacrypolus Enderlein, 1936

3.1. *Agromyza albipennis* Meigen, 1830

Synonyms: *Agromyza albohyalinata* Zetterstedt, 1848

Agromyza dubitata Malloch, 1913

Agromyza fennica Griffiths, 1963

Common name: black wheat leaf miner

Material examined: 30 specimens, 6♀, 8♂ in *Medicago sativa* L. (Fabaceae) on 15.iv.2020 and , 2♀, 2♂ in *Trigonella foenum-graecum* L. (Fabaceae) on 21.ii.2020 from Baghdad; , 3♀, 3♂ in *Hordeum vulgare* on 10.iv.2020 from Al-Najaf; , 4♀, 2♂ in *Meloletis indica* on 10.iv.2020. from Kerbala.

Distribution: Iraq [15]; Denmark, Finland, Norway, Sweden, Germany [16] Austria, Belarus, Corsica, Czech Republic, Estonia, European Turkey, Finland, Hungary, Italian mainland, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Slovakia, Spanish mainland and Switzerland; Also recorded in Canada, Japan and China [17]; Netherlands, Luxembourg , Belgium [18]; Turkey [19] Portugal [20].

3.2. *Agromyza megalopsis* Hering, 1933

Material examined: 4 specimens, 2♀, 2♂ in *Triticum aestivum* L. (Poaceae) on 30.iii. 2020 from Baghdad.

Distribution: Iraq [21]; in Europe, it's distributed from Poland to Spain and from France to Crete [22]; Bulgaria, Corfu, Crete and Croatia [23]; Former Yugoslavia; Egypt, Cyprus, Saudi Arabia, Turkey, Uzbekistan, Morocco [24].

3.3. *Agromyza nana* Meigen, 1830

Synonyms: *Agromyza anthracipes* (Rondani, 1875)

Agromyza brevinervis (Rondani, 1875)

Agromyza medicaginis Robineau-Desvoidy, 1851

Agromyza trifolii Kaltenbach, 1872

Domomyza anthracipes Rondani, 1875

Domomyza brevinervis Rondani, 1875

Material examined: 20 specimens, 6♀♀, 6 ♂♂ in *Melilotus indeca* (L.) All. (Fabaceae) at 13.ii.2020 from Kerbala; 6♀♀, 2 ♂♂ in *Medicago sativa* L. (Fabaceae) on 4.ii.2020. From Baghdad.

Distribution: Iraq [25] Palearctic Region [26]; Turkey [19] Portugal [20].

3.4. *Agromyza nigrescens* Hendel, 1920

Synonyms: *Agromyza heringi* Meijere, 1925

Agromyza japonica Tsujita, 1951

Agromyza microchaeta Hendel, 1920

Agromyza oycoviensis Beiger, 1960

Common name: Geranium leaf miner

Material examined: 4 specimens, 3♀♀, 1 ♂ in *Geranium dissectum* L. (Geraniaceae) on 3.iii.2020 from Baghdad.

Distribution: Iraq [15]; Denmark, Finland, Germany, Norway [16]; Turkey [19]; Netherlands, Greece, Luxembourg, UK, Switzerland, Spain, Japan, Croatia, Cyprus, Colombia, Italy, Sweden, Austria, Switzerland, Estonia [27].

Genus, *Melanagromyza* Hendel, 1920

Synonym: *Limnoagromyza* Malloch, 1921

3.5. *Melanagromyza azawii* Spencer, 1973

Material examined: This species previously collected from stem of *Vicia faba* L. (Fabaceae) and *Sesamum indicum* L. (Pedaliaceae) on July 1979 [15].

Distribution: Iraq and Greece [15]; Palaeartic Region [29]; India and Somalia [30]; Secretariat, 2021b).

Genus, *Phytoliriomyza* Hendel, 1931

Synonyms: *Lemurimyza* Spencer, 1965

Nesomyza Spencer, 1973

Pteridomyza Nowakowski, 1962

Xyraeomyia Frick, 1952

3.6. *Phytoliriomyza oasis* (Becker, 1907)

Synonym: *Agromyza oasis* Becker, 1907

Material examined: We cannot collect this species but previously recorded on March in Mousl [15].

Distribution: Iraq [15]; Kyrgyzstan, Lithuania, Morocco, Poland, Spain, Sweden, Turkey and Uzbekistan [22]; Turkey [19]; Portugal [20]; Norway and Greece [27].

Genus: *Ophiomyia* Braznikov, 1897

Synonyms: *Aulomyza* Enderlein, 1936

Carinagromyza Sasakawa, 1954

Siphonomyza Enderlein, 1936

Siridomyza Enderlein, 1936

Solenomyza Enderlein, 1936

Stiropomyza Enderlein, 1936

Stirops Enderlein, 1936

Tylomyza Hendel, 1931

3.7. *Ophiomyia phaseoli* (Tryon, 1951)

Synonyms: *Agromyza destructor* Malloch, 1916

Agromyza fabae Tryon, 1897

Agromyza fabalis Jack, 1953

Agromyza phaseoli Coquillett, 1899

Ophiomyia gangetica Garg, 1971

Ophiomyia sanctuarii Singh & Ipe, 1973

Oscinis fabae Tryon, 1897

Oscinis phaseoli Tryon, 1895

Common name: Bean fly; snap bean fly.

Material examined: 10 specimens, (5♀, 5♂) in *Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp. (Fabaceae) on 5.v.2020 from Abu-Ghraib/ Baghdad.

Distribution: Iraq [15]; (Spencer, 1981); Afrotropical, Australian, Oriental and Palearctic Regions [29]; Turkey [19]; Bangladesh [31].

Subfamily, Phytomyzinae

Genus, *Calycomyza* Hendel, 1931

3.8. *Calycomyza humeralis* (Roser, 1840)

Synonyms: *Agromyza atripes* Brischke, 1881

Agromyza bellidis Kaltenbach, 1873

Agromyza humeralis von Roser, 1840

Calycomyza bellidis (Kaltenbach, 1873)

Calycomyza humerella (von Roser, 1840)

Material examined: 4 specimens, 3♀ and 1♂ in *Tripolium pannonicum* subsp. *Tripolium* (L.) Greuter (Asteraceae) on 4.iii.2020 from Tarmiyah/ Baghdad.

Distribution: Iraq [15]; Turkey [19]; Argentina, Germany, Bulgaria, Norway, Switzerland, Netherlands, UK, South Africa, Zimbabwe, Ethiopia, Australia, Canada, USA [30].

Genus, *Cerodontha* Rondani, 1861

Synonyms: *Cerodonta* Hendel, 1910

Cerodonta Hering, 1926

3.9. *Cerodontha denticornis* (Panzer, 1806)

Synonyms: *Agromyza acuticornis* Meigen, 183

Agromyza confinis Meigen, 1830

Agromyza nigratarsis Meigen, 1830

Agromyza tarsella Zetterstedt, 1848

Ceratomyza nigriventris Strobl, 1900

Ceratomyza nigroscutellata Strobl, 1900

Ceratomyza semivittata Strobl, 1909

Cerodontha acuticornis (Meigen, 1830)

Cerodontha confinis (Meigen, 1830)

Cerodontha ghooma Singh & Ipe, 1973

Cerodontha lacustris Garg, 1971

Cerodontha meigenii (Fallén, 1823)

Cerodontha narkandae Singh & Ipe, 1973

Cerodontha nigriscutellata (Strobl, 1900)

Cerodontha nigratarsis (Meigen, 1830)

Cerodontha nigriventris (Strobl, 1900)

Cerodontha semivittata (Strobl, 1909)

Cerodontha tarsella (Zetterstedt, 1848)

Cerodontha testae Singh & Ipe, 1973

Chlorops denticornis Panzer, 1806

Chlorops meigeni Pa 1984

Chlorops meigenii Fallén, 1823

Material examined: 1 specimen in *Alopecurus partensis* L. (Poaceae) on 15.iii.2020 from Sulaymaniyah city.

Distribution: Iraq [15]; Iran [32]; Turkey [19]; Albania, Andorra, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech, Dalmatia, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, UK, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Maltese Islands, Montenegro, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, North Africa, Central and East Asia [20].

3.10. *Cerodontha luctuosa* (Meigen, 1830)

Synonyms: *Agromyza luctuosa* Meigen, 1830

Cerodontha effusi (Karl, 1926)

Dizygomyza effusi Karl, 1926

Material examined: 2 ♀♀, specimens in *Juncus effuses* L. (Juncaceae) on 17.iii.2020.

Distribution: Iraq[15]; Turkey[19]; Albania, Austria, Belgium, Belarus, Czech, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Russia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, former Yugoslavia, Israel, Tunisia, China, Japan, Uzbekistan, Canada and United States[20].

Genus, *Chromatomyia* Hardy, 1849

3.11. *Chromatomyia horticola* Goureau, 1851

Synonyms: *Chromatomyia bidensivora* (Séguy, 1951)

Chromatomyia cucumidis (Macquart, 1854)

Chromatomyia fediae (Kaltenbach, 1860)

Chromatomyia lactucae (Vimmer, 1928)

Chromatomyia linariae (Kaltenbach, 1862)

Chromatomyia meliloti (Brischke, 1882)

Chromatomyia nainiensis (Garg, 1971)

Chromatomyia pisi (Kaltenbach, 1864)

Chromatomyia subaffinis (Malloch, 1914)

Chromatomyia tropaeoli (Dufour, 1857)

Napomyza lactucae Vimmer, 1928

Phytomyza bidensivora Séguy, 1951

Phytomyza cucumidis Macquart, 1854

Phytomyza fediae Kaltenbach, 1860

Phytomyza horticola Goureau, 1851

Phytomyza linariae Kaltenbach, 1862

Phytomyza meliloti Brischke, 1882

Phytomyza nainiensis Garg, 1971

Phytomyza pisi Kaltenbach, 1864

Phytomyza subaffinis Malloch, 1914

Phytomyza tropaeoli Dufour, 1857

Common name: Pea leaf miner

Material examined: 45 specimens; 6♀♀, 6 ♂♂ in *Lepidium darba* L. (Brassicaceae) on 3.iii.2020 from Tarmyiah/ Baghdad; 4♀♀, 5 ♂♂ in *Sonchus* sp. on 10.iii.2020 from Nasiriya/ Thi- Qar; 8♀♀ and 6♂♂ in *Carthamus lanatus* on 20.iii.2020 from Basra; 5♀♀, 5 ♂♂ in *Cucurbita pepo* on 29.iii.2020 from Samarra.

Distribution: Iraq[15]; Turkey[33]; Portugal[20]; Norway, UK, Germany, Sweden, Netherlands, Finland, Pakistan, Korea, China, Japan, India, Portugal, South Africa, Eritrea, , Finland, Spain, Israel, Malta, Kenya, Ethiopia, Afghanistan, Zimbabwe, Italy, Denmark, Hungary and Austria[30].

Genus, *Japanagromyza* Sasakawa, 1958

3.12. *Japanagromyza salicifolii* Collin, 1911

Synonyms: *Agromyza salicifolii* Collin, 1911

Material examined: 3♀♀ specimens in poplar trees and *Quercus* L. (Fagaceae) on 4.iv.2020 from Mosul.

Distribution: Iraq [15] (Spencer, 1981); Palearctic Region [29]; Turkey [19]; Portugal [20].

Genus, *Liriomyza* Mik, 1894

Synonyms: *Agrophila* Liroy, 1864

Antineura Melander, 1913

Haplomyza Hendel, 1914

Praspedomyza Hendel, 1931

Triticomyza Blanchard, 1938

3.13. *Liriomyza brassicae* (Riley, 1885)

Synonyms: *Liriomyza hawaiiensis* Frick, 1952

Liriomyza ornephila Garg, 1971

Oscinis brassicae Riley, 1885

Phytomyza mitis Curran, 1931

Material examined: 50 specimens, 10♀♀, 6 ♂♂ in *Medicago sativa* L. (Fabaceae) on 10.v. 2020 from Basra; 6♀♀, 6 ♂♂ in *Pistum sativum* on 17.iii.2020 from Kerbala; 10♀♀, 10 ♂♂ in *Vigna mungo* (L.) Hepper (Fabaceae) on 20.iii.2020 from Baghdad; 1♀, 1 ♂ in *Dolichos sesuipedialis* on 4.iv.2020 from Baghdad.

Distribution: Iraq [25]; Ethiopian, Australian, Nearctic. Neotropical and Palaearctic regions [29]; Turkey [19].

3.14. *Liriomyza bryoniae* (Kaltenbach, 1858)

Synonyms: *Agromyza bryoniae* Kaltenbach, 1858

Liriomyza citrulli Rohdendorf, 1950

Liriomyza hydrocotylae Hering, 1930

Liriomyza mercurialis Hering, 1932

Liriomyza nipponalia Sasakawa, 1961

Liriomyza solani Hering, 1927

Liriomyza triton Frey, 1945

Common name: Tomato Leaf-miner

Material examined: 40 specimens, 5♀♀, 5 ♂♂ in *Cucurbita maxima* Duchesne (Cucurbitaceae) on 21.iii.2020 from Kerbala; 8♀♀, 10 ♂♂ in *Cucumis melo* on 20.v.2020 from Baghdad; 6♀♀, 6 ♂♂ in *Melilotis indica* on 20.iv.2020 from Baghdad.

Distribution: Iraq [21]; Oriental and Palearctic Regions [29]; Turkey [19]; Portugal [20].

3.15. *Liriomyza congesta* (Becker, 1903)

Synonyms: *Agromyza congesta* Becker, 1903

Liriomyza centaureana Hering, 1936

Liriomyza leguminosarum Meijere, 1924

Liriomyza minima Hendel, 1931

Liriomyza nigripleura Ryden, 1956

Liriomyza parva Hendel, 1931

Liriomyza taraia Garg, 1971

Common name: Broad bean, bean and pea leaf-miner

Material examined: 20 specimens, 6♀♀, 6 ♂♂ in *Brassica rapa* L. (Brassicaceae) on 20.ii.2020 from Baghdad; 4♀♀, 4 ♂♂ in *Melilotis indica* on 28.iv.2020 from Kerbala.

Distribution: Iraq [25]; Oriental and Palearctic Regions [29]; Turkey [19]; Portugal [20].

3.16. *Liriomyza orbona* (Meigen, 1830)

Synonyms: *Agromyza fuscolimbata* Strobl, 1900

Agromyza orbona Meigen, 1830

Liriomyza fuscolimbata (Strobl, 1900)

Liriomyza orbonella Hendel, 1931

Material examined: previously recorded 1♀♂ from south of Mosul on 13.iii.1979 [15].

Distribution: Iraq [15]; Palearctic Region [29]; Turkey [19]; Portugal [20].

3.17. *Liriomyza sativae* Blanchard, 1938

Synonyms: *Agromyza subpusilla* Frost, 1943

Lemurimyza lycopersicae Pla & de la Cruz, 1981

Liriomyza canomarginis Frick, 1952

Liriomyza guytona Freeman, 1958

Liriomyza minutiseta Frick, 1952

Liriomyza munda Frick, 1957

Liriomyza propepusilla Frost, 1954

Liriomyza properpusilla Frost, 1954

Liriomyza pullata Frick, 1952

Liriomyza verbenicola Hering, 1951

Common name: Vegetable leaf miner

Material examined: 30 specimens, 6♀♀, 6 ♂♂ in *Melilotis indica* (L.) All. (Fabaceae) on 25.iv.2020 from Baghdad; 10♀♀, 8 ♂♂ in *Cucurbita moschata* Duchesne (Cucurbitaceae) on 20.x.2020 from Duhok, North of Iraq.

Distribution: Iraq [34]; Ethiopian, Australian, Nearctic. Neotropical and Palearctic Regions [29]; Bangladesh [31].

3.18. *Liriomyza strigata* Meigen, 1830

3.18. *Liriomyza strigata* Meigen, 1830

Synonyms: *Agromyza galeopsios* Hardy, 1853

Agromyza pumila Meigen, 1830

Agromyza strigata Meigen, 1830

Agromyza violae Curtis, 1844

Liriomyza galeopsios (Hardy, 1853)

Liriomyza pumila (Meigen, 1830)

Liriomyza violae (Curtis, 1844)

Material examined: 20 specimens, 8♀♀, 8♂♂ in *Brassica rapa* L. (Brassicaceae) on 2.iv.2020 from Al-Nejef; 3♀♀, 1♂ in *Pisum sativum* on 10.iv.2020.

Distribution: Iraq [21]; (Oriental and Palearctic Regions [29]; Turkey [19].

3.19. *Liriomyza trifolii* Burgess, 1880

Synonyms: *Agromyza phaseolunata* Frost, 194

Agromyza phaseolunulata Frost, 1943

Liriomyza alliovora Frick, 1955

Liriomyza phaseolunulata (Frost, 1943)

Oscinis trifolii Burgess, 188

Common name: American serpentine Leaf-miner

Material examined: 10 specimens, (6♀♀, 4♂♂) in *Ricinus communis* L. (Euphorbiaceae) on 28.x.2020 from Baghdad.

Distribution: Iraq [35]; Ethiopian, Australian, Nearctic, Neotropical and Palaeartic Regions [29]; Turkey [33].

Genus, *Napomyza* Westwood, 1840

Synonyms: *Dinevra* Lioy, 1864

Napomyia Schiner, 1868

3.20. *Napomyza lateralis* (Fallen, 1823)

Synonym: *Phytomyza lateralis* Fallén, 1823

Common name: Calendula fly

Material examined: 2specimens, 1♀1♂ in *Stachys* sp. on 22.iii.2020 from Kirkuk.

Distribution: Iraq [15]; Nearctic and Palaeartic Regions [29]; Turkey [19]; Portugal [20].

Genus: *Phytomyza* Fallén, 1810

Synonyms: *Lonicera* Meijere, 1924

Phythyomyza Rondani, 1874

Phytomyia Haliday, 1833

3.21. *Phytomyza ferulivora* Griffiths, 1956

Material examined: 10 specimens, (4♀♀, 6♂♂) in *Daucus carota* L. (Apiaceae) on 10.iii.2020 from Baghdad.

Distribution: Iraq [15]; Palaeartic Region [29].

3.22. *Phytomyza ranunculi* (Schrank, 1803)

Synonyms: *Musca ranunculi* Schrank, 1803

Phytomyza albipes Meigen, 1830

Phytomyza cinereovittata Zetterstedt, 1848

Phytomyza cinerovittata Zetterstedt, 1848

Phytomyza citrina Roser, 1840

Phytomyza flava Fallen, 1823

Phytomyza flaveola Fallen, 1810

Phytomyza flavoscutellata Fallen, 1823

Phytomyza flavoscutellata Meigen, 1830

Phytomyza flavotibialis Strobl, 1902

Phytomyza incisa Macquart, 1835

Phytomyza islandica Ryden, 1953
Phytomyza maculipes Brulle, 1833
Phytomyza maculipes Zetterstedt, 1848
Phytomyza pallida Meigen, 1830
Phytomyza pentalinearum Kuroda, 1954
Phytomyza praecox Meigen, 1830
Phytomyza ranunculi Kaltenbach, 1867
Phytomyza ranunculi Robineau-Desvoidy, 1851
Phytomyza scutellata Meigen, 1830
Phytomyza tenuipennis Singh & Ipe, 1973

Material examined: 4 specimens, (2♀♀, 2♂♂) in *Anemon cornaria* L. (Ranunculaceae) on 30.v.2020 from Baghdad.
Distribution: Iraq [15]; Nearctic, Oriental and Palaearctic Regions [29]; Turkey [19]; Portugal [20].

3.23. *Phytomyza rufipes* Meigen, 1830

Synonyms: *Phytomyza bistrigata* Strobl, 1906
Phytomyza brassicae Hardy, 1853
Phytomyza femoralis Brischke, 1881
Phytomyza genislatissimus Strobl, 1893
Phytomyza ruficornis Zetterstedt, 1848
Phytomyza sulphuripes Meigen, 1830
Phytomyza sulphuripes Meigen, 1830

Common name: Cabbage leaf-miner

Material examined: 15 specimens, (8♀♀, 7♂♂) in *Brassicae rapa* L. (Brassicaceae) on 28.ii.2020 from Basra.
Distribution: Iraq [15]; Nearctic, Neotropical and Palaearctic Regions [29]; Turkey [19]; Portugal [20].

3.24. *Phytomyza tetrasticha* Hendel, 1927

Material examined: 12 specimens, (8♀♀, 4♂♂) in *Mentha longifolia* (L.) L. (Lamiaceae) on 20.iii.2020 from Baghdad.
Distribution: Iraq [15]; Palaearctic Region [29]; Turkey [19]; Portugal [20].

Family: Anthomyiidae

Genus, *Pegomya* Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Synonyms: *Pegomaya* Macquart, 1835
Patemia Albuquerque, 1954
Forai Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830
Forie Macquart, 1835

3.25. *Pegomya bicolor* Wiedemann, 1817

Synonyms: *Anthomyia mitis* Meigen, 1826
Anthomyia rumicis Bouché, 1834
Pegomya cinereorufa (Ringdahl, 1930)
Pegomya mitis (Meigen, 1826)
Pegomyia cinereorufa Ringdahl, 1930
Pegomyia sapporensis Kato, 1941
Zabia longipes Robineau-Desvoidy, 1830

Material examined: 4 specimens, 2♀♀, ♂♂2 in *Rumex sanguineus* L. (Polygonaceae) on 25.iv.2020 from Baghdad.

Distribution: Iraq [36]; Japan[37]; Czech Republic[38]; India[39]; Finland[40]; Scotland[41]; Iran[42]; UK [43]; Palaearctic [44]; Korea[11].

3.26. *Pegomya cunicularia* (Rondani, 1886)

Synonyms: *Chorthophila cunicularia* Rondani, 1866
Chorthophila cunicularia Rondani, 1866
Pegomya mixta Villeneuve, 1922
Pegomyia tristriata Stein, 1908

Material examined: 5 specimens, 3♀♀, ♂♂2 in *Chenopodium murale* L. (Amaranthaceae) on 14.iv.2020 from Baghdad.

Distribution: Iraq [36]; Canary Island [45]; Spin [46]; Korea [11].

3.27. *Pegomya hyoscyami* (Panzer, 1809)

Synonyms: *Anthomyia hyoscyami* Panzer, 1809

Chorthophila stlemba Giglio-Tos, 1893

Material examined: 4 specimens, 2♀♀, ♂♂2 in *Chenopodium* sp. L. (Amaranthaceae) in ix.2020 from Baghdad.

Distribution: Iraq[47]; Cyprus, Jordan, Israel, Egypt, Turkey, Libya, Europe[48]; Finland[40] Scotland[41]; Turkey[49]; Iran[42]; Korea[11]; Russia[50].

3.28. *Pegomya terebrans*(Rondani, 1866)

Synonyms: *Pegomya sylvatica* (Rondani, 1866)

Chorthophila brasiliensis Rondani, 1866

Pegomya incisa Villeneuve, 1923

Pegomya unicolor Strobl, 1909

Material examined: 4 specimens, 2♀♀, and ♂♂2 in *Carduus nutans* subsp. *Platypus* (Lang) **Greuter (Asteraceae)** on 18.1.2020 from Baghdad.

Distribution: Iraq [36]; Spin [46].

Family: Drosophilidae

Genus, *Scaptomyza* Hady, 1850

Synonyms: *Alloscaptomyza* Hackman, 1962

Boninoscaptomyza Okada, 1972

Bunostoma Malloch, 1932

Ctenoscaptomyza Frey, 1954

Dentiscaptomyza Hardy, 1965

Euscaptomyza Séguy, 1938

Exalloscaptomyza Hardy, 1965

Lauxanomyza Tsacas & Cogan, 1976

Macrosaptomyza Frey, 1954

Metascaptomyza Hackman, 1959

Rosenwaldia Malloch, 1934

Scaptomyzella Hendel, 1928

Scaptomyzetta Hendel, 1928

Tantalia Malloch, 1938

Tristanomyia Frey, 1954

Trogloscaptomyza Frey, 1954

3.29. *Scaptomyza flava* (Fallen, 1823)

Synonyms: *Drosophila flava* Fallén, 1823

Notiphila flaveola Meigen, 1830

Scaptomyza apiralis Duda, 1921

Scaptomyza flaveola (Meigen, 1830)

Material examined: 20 Specimens, 5♀♀, 5♂♂ in *Raphanus raphanistrum* subsp. *sativus* (L.) Domin (Brassicaceae) on 20.iii.2020 from Basra and 6♀♀, 4♂♂ on 30.iii.2020. From Baghdad.

Distribution: Iraq [51]; New Zealand [52]; Fennoscandia and Denmark [53]; UAE [54] Hawaii [55]; Malta [56]; Arizona [57]; UK [58].

Order: Lepidoptera

Family: Gelechiidae

Genus, *Tuta* Kieffer & Jörgensen, 1910

3.30. *Tuta bsoluta* (Meyrick, 1917)

Synonyms: *Phthorimaea Absolute* Meyrick, 1917

Gnorimoschema absoluta (Meyrick, 1917)

Common names: Tomato leafminer and tomato pinworm.

Materials examined: 55 Adult specimens in *Solanum lycopersicum* L. (Solanaceae) 10♀♀, 10♂♂ on 5.v.2020 from Baghdad; 8♀♀, 7♂♂ in Plastic houses on 20.vi.2020 from Kut; 12♀♀, 8♂♂ on 10.vii.2020 from Kerbala.

Distribution: Iraq [59] Argentina, Brazil, Paraguay, Venezuela [60]; Spain [61]; European and North African [62].

Family, Gracillariidae

Genus, *Phyllocnistis* Zeller, 1848

3.31. *Phyllocnistis citrella* Stainton, 1856

Synonyms: *Phyllocnistis citricola* (Shiraki, 1913)

Phyllocnistis minutella van Deventer, 1904

Common name: Citrus Leaf Minor (CLM)

Material examined: Many leaves of mandarin orange *Citrus reticulata* Blanco (Rutaceae) were infested by CLM on 22.iii.2020 from Baghdad; and Citrus L. (Rutaceae) infested leaves collected on 10.ii.2020 from Kerbala.

Distribution: Iraq[63]; Egypt[64]; Morocco[65]; Syria[66]; Pakistan[67]; Turkey[68]; Greece[69]; Algeria[70].

4. Conclusion

The investigation showed the agromyzid flies the most important leaf miners attacked many various host plant types and caused damages. The research noticed that the insects were found in the leaves of Fabaceae plants more than other Families.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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